

DESIGN FOR MANUFACTURABILITY (DFM) FOR COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The present paper proposes a DFM strategy for composites. The main feature of this strategy is to include process modeling in the early stages of design to assess the technical and economic feasibility of candidate manufacturing processes. Some of the commonly used manufacturing processes for composites are discussed as regards their capabilities and limitations. These processes include lay-up molding, filament winding, resin transfer molding, and pultrusion. A unified approach to process modeling is described together with a brief survey of available process models.

1. INTRODUCTION

Anderson, in his book [1], defines Design for Manufacturability (DFM) as the practice of designing products with manufacturing in mind. Specifically, in DFM, considerations are given early in the design phase to the steps involved in manufacturing, such as materials selection, part standardization, fabrication, assembly, testing, repair, and maintenance. It is a team approach to design, involving not only designers but also manufacturing engineers, materials engineers, test engineers, marketing engineers, and so forth. The rationale for DFM is to identify possible manufacturing-related problems early at the design phase so that costly corrective measures are not needed belatedly. Consequently, lower cost, better quality, and timely delivery are the main benefits of DFM.

The presence of fibers in composites presents both advantages and disadvantages in manufacturing. On the one hand, some of the conventional manufacturing processes developed for non-composites cannot be used for composites. On the other hand, some unique processes are possible with composites because of the presence of fibers. The

applicability of these composites manufacturing processes also depends on the geometry of the parts to be produced. Thus, design of composite parts must take into account the feasibility of the manufacturing processes to be used later.

There is another reason why the design engineer should be familiar with the available manufacturing processes including their advantages and limitations. When designing with composites, fiber architecture must be specified because it controls the structural performance. However, the specific fiber architecture that is called for in the design may not be possible with certain manufacturing processes. Thus, incompatible manufacturing processes must be identified as early as possible.

The present paper describes some of the commonly used manufacturing processes and what provisions should be made in the design phase for each of these processes. It is proposed that manufacturability be assessed using process models, both extant and to be developed. The discussion is limited to thermosetting polymer matrix composites reinforced with continuous fibers.

2. COMMON MANUFACTURING PROCESSES

Manufacturing of composite parts generally requires three steps: fiber impregnation, forming, and consolidation. In some processes, the three steps are performed separately while in others, they may be carried out sequentially on line. In all processes, heat and force are applied to produce fully cured, void-free parts with good fiber/matrix bonding. Four of the commonly used manufacturing processes are briefly described in the following [2,3].

2.1 Lay-Up Molding Lay-up molding is the most widely used manufacturing process especially for aircraft parts. In the process, unidirectional or fabric-reinforced prepreg plies are cut into the desired shapes and stacked together with proper ply orientations on a mold to form a laminated part. The part is then covered with processing aids such as peel plies and bleeder cloths as needed, and is debulked inside a vacuum bag. The whole assembly is placed inside an autoclave and cured under vacuum and external pressure.

Although the lay-up molding combined with autoclave curing yields high quality parts, it is as yet labor intensive, and hence is an expensive process. Lay-up of unidirectional plies over surfaces with double curvatures should be avoided unless the radii of curvature are large. Fabric plies should be used if surfaces are uneven. Still, highly uneven surfaces may lead to wrinkling in the cured laminate.

2.2 Filament Winding Filament winding is ideally suited for axisymmetric structures with convex surfaces. The basic step involved is the winding of fiber tows over a mandrel. The so-called dry winding uses tows that are already impregnated with resin by the material supplier. In wet winding, however, dry tows are impregnated with resin on-line during winding.

Filament winding invariably results in fiber cross-overs, which reduce both stiffness and strength. Therefore, they must be included early in design. Also, axial winding is much more difficult than helical winding, and hence should be avoided if an alternate winding pattern can be found. In certain areas such as near the boss openings of a pressure vessel, the wall thickness will be much larger than in the other areas. Design should take into account such inherent limitations of filament winding.

Excessive compaction of filament-wound cylinders through the application of external pressure can result in wrinkling of fiber layers. Thus, good compaction may have to be compromised for wrinkle-free layers.

2.3 Resin Transfer Molding Resin transfer molding consists of two main steps: the fabrication of a fiber preform and the injection of resin into a mold containing the fiber preform. Fiber preforms having the near net shape are obtained through deformation processing of fabrics and strand mats. They can also be braided directly into the final shape without going through intermediate deformation processes. The presence of the fiber preform in the mold necessitates a higher injection pressure, and low viscosity is essential to facilitate the resin flow and fiber wetting.

A proper balance should be maintained between the structural properties and the formability in selecting fiber preforms to be used. A tightly woven fabric may yield the desired mechanical properties, but it may not be amenable to deformation without broken fibers. The presence of a fiber preform in the mold may facilitate resin flow in one direction while hampering it in other directions. Such anisotropic resin flow may place a limit on possible fiber orientations and will affect the mold design.

2.4 Pultrusion Pultrusion is a process for fabricating profiles of constant cross section. Dry fiber preforms such as fabrics and strand mats are pulled continuously through a succession of a resin bath, forming guides, and a heated die to emerge as a fully cured profile.

Pultrusion is not feasible unless a sufficient amount of fibers is oriented in the pull direction, i.e., along the axis of the profile. Consequently, pultruded profiles tend to be

weaker in the transverse direction. Furthermore, fiber preforms should be stacked so as to enable the part to be pulled without disturbing the fiber architecture.

The pressure needed for compaction is provided by the resin back flow and the thermal expansion of the part, both near the die entrance. However, this pressure is not sufficient to provide the same degree of compaction possible in autoclave curing. Therefore, pultruded parts tend to have higher void contents.

3. DFM APPROACH FOR COMPOSITES

A suggested DFM procedure for composites starts with the selection of a part geometry once functional requirements are specified, Fig. 1. Since the high strength and high stiffness of composites are obtained from the fibers, the part geometry should be chosen so that these fibers are kept continuous by minimizing assembly and joining. Once fibers are cut, their effectiveness is degraded and the resulting part is not structurally efficient.

The next step is to choose a candidate fiber architecture. For the chosen architecture, the resulting properties can be predicted using the available micromechanics models [4,5]. Different fiber preforms provide different fiber architectures. Unidirectional plies contain straight fibers which offer the best properties in the fiber direction. However, their drapeability over curved surfaces is not good. A much better drapeability is obtained with fabric plies [6,7]. Unfortunately, the fiber crimp which provides good drapeability leads to lower mechanical properties.

While unidirectional and fabric plies need to be stacked up to yield the desired thickness, the absence of any fibers across ply interfaces results in low interlaminar strength of these laminates. The interlaminar weakness inherent in laminates can be circumvented by stitching through the thickness or by using 3-dimensional braids. Yet, the sacrifices in in-plane properties should be carefully weighed against the gains in out-of-plane properties.

The thickness of a composite part depends on the thickness and number of constituent plies used. If the exact part thickness is to be obtained by controlling the resin compaction, the resulting fiber volume and void content may turn out to be something other than desired. Also, ply orientations should be dispersed as much as possible. Lumping of plies with the same orientation makes them more vulnerable to ply cracking [8], and hence should be avoided. Even for the same in-plane stiffness, the bending and torsional rigidities change with the stacking sequence. Thus the exact stacking sequence must be specified during design.

As mentioned earlier, the selection of a manufacturing process depends on the part geometry. That is, a long profile of constant cross section is most convenient for pultrusion whereas a circular cylinder is an ideal candidate for filament winding. However, the final selection should also take into account the quality and fiber architecture required. For example, filament winding invariably introduces fiber cross-overs, and pultruded products tend to have higher void content than autoclave-cured ones.

Once candidate processes are chosen, their technical feasibility should be checked out through process modeling. The final assessment of manufacturability should be based not only on technical feasibility but also on cost, quality and delivery time. Since processability is of prime importance in DFM, process modeling will be discussed in detail for each of the manufacturing processes introduced earlier.

4. PROCESS MODELING

During processing the internal state as well as the external geometry of the part changes under the influence of external stimuli. The main goal of process modeling is to predict the changes in the internal state and external geometry as a function of process parameters. An overview of process modeling is shown in Fig. 2, where specific parameters involved are also listed.

The chemical changes occurring in the matrix resin during cure are collectively described by the degree of cure ϕ . The degree of cure at time t is conveniently defined as the heat of reaction to time t divided by the total heat associated with complete reaction. Thus, the degree of cure varies from zero, when there is no cure at all, to the maximum value of unity, when cure is complete. The time rate of cure depends on the present degree of cure as well as on the temperature. A number of cure kinetics equations have been proposed so far [9,10,11]. An example is given by [10]

$$\frac{d\phi}{dt} = (k_1 + k_2 \phi^m) (1 - \phi)^n \quad (1)$$

where k_1 and k_2 are rate constants, which depend on temperature, and m and n are constants.

The thermophysical properties of the matrix resin that affect processing are the density ρ , the specific heat c , the thermal conductivity K , and the coefficient of thermal expansion α . Representation of mechanical properties throughout the entire processing is not well understood at present although some attempts have been made to use complex moduli measured ultrasonically [12]. A more common approach is to treat the matrix resin as a

viscous liquid until it gels. After gelation, the resin becomes a viscoelastic solid. The fluid viscosity μ controls the resin flow whereas the viscoelastic creep compliance $S(t)$ affects the development of residual stresses. All these physical, thermal and mechanical properties depend on the degree of cure and the temperature [13]:

$$(\rho, \alpha, c, K, \mu, S) = f(\phi, T) \quad (2)$$

The changes occurring inside the part are governed by the three balance principles:

$$\text{Balance of mass: } dp/dt + \rho \partial v_i / \partial x_i = 0 \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Balance of energy: } \rho du/dt = \sigma_{ij} \partial v_j / \partial x_i - \partial q_i / \partial x_i + r \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Balance of linear momentum: } \partial \sigma_{ji} / \partial x_j = \rho \partial v_i / dt \quad (5)$$

Here v_i is the velocity vector, u the internal energy density, q_i the heat flux vector, r the time rate of heat being generated per unit mass, and σ_{ij} is the stress tensor. It is noted that the balance of mass plays the key role in the resin flow while the balance of energy controls the temperature distribution. The balance of linear momentum or the resulting equilibrium equation governs the development of residual stresses.

The boundary conditions to be used depend on the process parameters. These process parameters include not only heat input and pressure application to the part but also the type of mold and processing aids used. For example, the amount of resin to be squeezed out can be controlled by varying the number of bleeder cloths.

Overall, process modeling involves the solution of Equations (1) through (5) under the appropriate boundary conditions dictated by the imposed process parameters. The main output from the modeling is the degree of cure, the degree of compaction, and the residual stresses throughout the part.

In many cases, a direct application of Eqs. (1) through (5) is not practicable. Rather, these equations are modified to facilitate their solution. The usual procedure is to solve the energy balance equation together with the cure kinetics equation to determine the temperature field and the degree of cure. The results are then used as input to solve the mass balance equation for the resin flow and compaction, and also to solve the equilibrium equation for the residual stress distribution.

4.1 Fiber Architecture The drapeability of a fabric depends on how it is woven. At the local level, in-plane deformation is possible only in shear. Analytical methods are available to predict fabric drapeability [6,7]. A tightly woven fabric is not much drapeable, and hence is difficult to use over curved surfaces. Fabrics should be able to absorb any slack resulting from uneven surfaces; otherwise, wrinkling will result. Therefore, the drapeability is one of the major selection criteria for fabrics in lay-up molding, resin transfer molding and pultrusion.

Fiber cross-over patterns inherent in filament winding depend on the winding parameters such as tow width, winding angle, and dwell angle [14]. Since fibers are not straight at cross-over points, the strength of a filament-wound tube will depend on its fiber cross-over pattern. Thus, one should be able to predict the fiber cross-over pattern before actual winding.

Fiber paths in a braid can be determined from the braiding parameters [15]. Since only a certain number of braiding patterns are possible with a chosen machine, requirements from structural design should be reconciled with the manufacturability of the desired pattern.

4.2 Temperature Distribution and Degree of Cure The temperature distribution is obtained from the energy balance equation usually with the resin flow neglected. The heat source r represents the exothermic reaction of the resin. Analytical models are available for curing of flat panels [9,11,13,16] and filament-wound cylinders [17-19] as well as for pultrusion [20-22].

4.3 Resin Flow and Compaction The compaction behavior has been modeled for flat panels [9,16,23], filament-wound cylinders [17-19], and pultrusion [20,23] while the resin flow through fiber preform has been analyzed for resin transfer molding [23-25]. The main approach is to rewrite the balance of mass equation using the fiber network as a reference frame. The problem is then treated as a flow through a deforming porous medium.

4.4 Residual Stresses Residual stresses develop mostly during the cool down phase of a cure cycle [26]. Although chemical shrinkage gives rise to residual stresses, much of these stresses are relaxed before cure is completed [27]. A viscoelastic analysis shows that the stress relaxation during cool down is rather small [28]. Residual stresses due to uneven cure in a thick laminate have also been predicted [11].

Residual stresses can also develop at round corners when the thickness changes due to compaction. These stresses combined with thermally induced stresses manifest themselves in the springing-in of angle sections.

In filament winding, residual stresses are induced by winding tension as well [17-19]. In fact, these stresses are believed to be responsible for wavy tows found after cure.

5. CONCLUSIONS

It is proposed that DFM for composites be based on the development and utilization of process models. At present, basic process models are available for some of the key manufacturing processes for composites. However, most of these models are for simple geometries and they need to be expanded to handle realistic processing conditions.

The knowledge gained from process simulation can also be used to develop expert-system-based intelligent process control systems [29-31]. This would speed up the manufacturing automation, opening the way for low-cost and high-quality manufacturing for composites.

The drapeability and formability of fiber preforms are the key in many manufacturing processes such as lay-up molding, resin transfer molding, and pultrusion. A better understanding of these properties is needed if composites are to be used in structures having complex geometries.

6. REFERENCES

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Figure 1. DFM Approach for Composites

State Parameters

- Material: chemical, physical, thermal, and mechanical properties
- Structural: voids, fiber architecture, fiber volume content, residual stresses

Physical Principles

- Mass Balance
- Energy Balance
- Momentum Balance

Process Parameters

- Force
- Heat
- Processing Aids
- Mold

Figure 2. Process Modeling